

Complex Formation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Zinc(II) with some Sulphonamides derived from Amino Acids

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Equilibrium study of the interaction of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) with *N*-benzenesulphonamides, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(R)COOH$ (formulated as HL) derived from the amino acids, viz serine ($R = CH_2OH$), threonine ($R = CH(CH_3)OH$) and methionine ($R = CH_2CH_2SCH_3$), by pH-metric method provided evidence of formation of a variety of complexes of the type $M(H_{-1}L)$, $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$, $M(H_{-1}L)(H_{-1}L)_2^{3-}$ and $M(H_{-2}L)_2^{2-}$. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants: K_{HL}^H , K_{M+L}^H , K_{M+2L}^H , $K_{M(H_{-1}L)_2}^H$ and $K_{M(H_{-2}L)_2}^H$ have been determined at three temperatures, 25, 35 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium having a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$). Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) associated with the complexation equilibria have been evaluated and correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligands and properties of the metal ions.

INTERESTING observations on the order of stabilities of metal-ligand complexes and variation of optical activity of the ligands *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine and *N*-*N'*-dibenzesulphonyl-L-cysteine as a function of pH and complex formation with metal ions have been described earlier¹. Unusual order ($K_2 > K_1$) of stabilities of Ni^{2+} complexes with *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine was assigned to the π -acidic nature of the thiol sulphur donor site of the ligand². It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to make a systematic study on metal-ligand interaction with the sulphonamido ligands, viz. *N*-benzenesulphonylserine (NBSS), *N*-benzenesulphonylthreonine (NBST) and *N*-benzenesulphonyl-dl-methionine (NBSM) having comparable structural features (1) as those of the ligand *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine³:

NBSS: $R = CH_2OH$; NBST: $R = CH(CH_3)OH$;
NBSM: $R = CH_2CH_2SCH_3$; NBSCL: $R = CH_2SH$

The present paper describes a pH-metric study of the complex formation of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ion with the ligands NBSS, NBST and NBSM at three temperatures 25, 35 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium having a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$). The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants and the thermodynamic parameters associated with the complexation equilibria have been evaluated and

correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligands and electronic structures of the metal ions.

Experimental

The ligands, NBSS, NBST and NBSM were synthesised by condensing the amino acids, serine, threonine and methionine, respectively with benzenesulphonyl chloride in alkaline medium ($pH \approx 10$) following the usual procedure described in the literature⁴⁻⁶ with slight modifications as and when required. NBSS was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, and NBSM and NBST were recrystallised from water. Purity of the compounds was checked from elemental analysis, determination of equivalent weight, m.p. and examination of uv and ir spectra. All the other reagents were either of A.R. quality or properly purified, and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified ethanol⁶.

Equilibrium study consisted of pH-metric titrations of solutions of known amounts of the ligands (NBSS, NBST and NBSM) containing known amount of free acid (HNO_3) in the absence and in the presence of known amount of metal ions at three temperatures 25, 35 and 45° (thermostated) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium, having a constant ionic strength, 0.2 M, maintained by adding requisite amounts of $NaNO_3$. Details of the procedure were the same as described earlier⁷⁻⁹.

pH measurements were made with a SYSTRONICS 335 digital pH meter accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit employing a special glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode. Hydrogen ion concentration at different pH meter readings were evaluated by

TABLE 1—PROTON—LIGAND AND METAL—LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS AT THREE TEMPERATURES IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL MEDIUM AND ASSOCIATED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Ionic strength, $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaNO₃)

System	Constants	Temperature (°C)			Thermodynamic parameters		
		25±1	35±1	45±1	$-\Delta G$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
NBSS-H	pK_{HL}^H	3.93	3.87	3.81	22	-8	100
NBSS-Co ²⁺	pK_{Co+L}^H	5.40	4.96	4.55	31	77	361
	pK_{Co+2L}^{2H}	11.32	10.58	9.87	65	132	651
	$pK_{Co(H-1L)_2}^H$	11.46	11.05	10.60	66	-77	-38
	$pK_{Co(H-1L)_2}^{2H}$	23.36	22.67	21.78	134	-143	-34
NBSS-Ni ²⁺	pK_{Ni+L}^H	5.32	4.13	4.86	31	39	231
	pK_{Ni+2L}^{2H}	11.32	10.95	10.46	65	76	470
	$pK_{Ni(H-1L)_2}^H$	10.46	10.06	9.56	60	-69	-29
NBSS-Zn ²⁺	pK_{Zn+L}^H	3.70	3.60	3.48	28	21	164
	pK_{Zn+2L}^{2H}	8.56	8.26	7.99	49	51	336
	$pK_{Zn(H-1L)_2}^H$	10.84	10.62	10.35	62	-44	63
	$pK_{Zn(H-1L)_2}^{2H}$	21.74	21.57	21.35	125	-35	81
NBST-H	pK_{HL}^H	4.05	4.01	3.96	23	-8	59
NBST-Co ²⁺	pK_{Co+L}^H	6.07	5.97	5.87	35	20	185
	pK_{Co+2L}^{2H}	12.37	12.20	12.05	71	31	340
NBST-Ni ²⁺	pK_{Ni+L}^H	5.23	4.09	4.93	30	28	176
	pK_{Ni+2L}^{2H}	11.83	11.60	11.38	68	40	361
NBST-Zn ²⁺	pK_{Zn+2L}^{2H}	9.04	8.88	8.72	52	27	172
NBSM-H	pK_{HL}^H	4.35	4.31	4.26	25	-9	55
NBSM-Co ²⁺	pK_{Co+L}^H	4.08	4.05	4.02	24	7	101
	pK_{Co+2L}^{2H}	9.93	9.86	9.80	57	12	227
NBSM-Ni ²⁺	pK_{Ni+L}^H	4.49	4.45	4.41	26	7	109
	pK_{Ni+2L}^{2H}	10.94	10.83	10.71	63	21	281
NBSM-Zn ²⁺	pK_{Zn+L}^H	4.57	4.52	4.45	26	10	122
	pK_{Zn+2L}^{2H}	9.61	9.52	9.40	55	16	240

incorporating corrections for mixed solvents by the usual procedures¹⁰⁻¹³. The necessary concentration variables required for the evaluation of the equilibrium constants were calculated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁴.

Proton—ligand and metal—ligand equilibria: All the three ligands (NBSS, NBST and NBSM) were titrated as monoprotic acids (HL) in the entire pH (2–12) range (Fig. 1) studied and offered a single buffer region (pH ≈ 2.5–5.0) corresponding to deprotonation of the carboxylic acid groups, of which the pK_{HL}^H values are stated in Table 1.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves at 35° in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at $\mu = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$): (1) 0.01 M HNO_3 , (2) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.001 M Co(NO_3)_2$, (3) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.001 M Ni(NO_3)_2$, (4) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.001 M Zn(NO_3)_2$, (5) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSS$, (6) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSS + 0.002 M Co(NO_3)_2$, (7) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSS + 0.002 M Ni(NO_3)_2$, (8) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSS + 0.002 M Zn(NO_3)_2$, (9) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBST$, (10) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBST + 0.002 M Co(NO_3)_2$, (11) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBST + 0.002 M Ni(NO_3)_2$, (12) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBST + 0.002 M Zn(NO_3)_2$, (13) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSM$, (14) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSM + 0.002 M Co(NO_3)_2$, (15) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSM + 0.002 M Ni(NO_3)_2$, and (16) 0.01 M $HNO_3 + 0.01 M NBSM + 0.002 M Zn(NO_3)_2$; initial volume = 25 ml, titrant : 0.125 M NaOH.

The buffer region corresponding to the carboxylic group deprotonation of the ligands was not

lowered by the presence of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions, moreover, the metal—ligand equilibria occurred at a higher pH range (5–9). These suggested non-involvement of the COOH group in the complexation equilibria. Release of two protons per metal ion was assigned to the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal—ligand complexes through the displacement of sulphonamide ($-SO_2NH-$) proton of the ligand, L^- ions by the metal ions ($M^{2+} = Co^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) according to the equilibria :

with simultaneous formation of the hydroxo complexes, *viz.* $M(OH)^+$ and $M(OH)_2$. The metal ion hydrolysis constants (K_M^H and K_{M+2L}^{2H}) were evaluated by analysing¹⁴ the pH-titration curves (curves 1, 2, 3 and 4, Fig. 1) of the two series of solutions containing (i) known amount of free acid (HNO_3) and (ii) known amounts of metal ions in presence of the same amount of free acid (HNO_3) as in (i). Formation of these hydroxo complexes were taken into consideration while calculating the formation constants, K_{M+L}^H and K_{M+2L}^{2H} by solving the formation function^{15,16} of the form :

$$\bar{n} = (ax + 2bx^2) / (1 + ax + bx^2) \quad (3)$$

where, $a = K_{M+L}^H \cdot K_M^H$, $b = K_{M+2L}^{2H} \cdot K_M^{2H}$ and $K_{M+2L}^{2H} = K_{M+L}^H \cdot K_{M(H_{-1}L)_2}^H$, $x = [L]/[H]$ and $\bar{n}$ = average number of protons released due to metal—ligand complex formation. The $\bar{n}$ and $\log x$ values were obtained by analysing¹⁴ the pH-titration curves (curves 1, 5–16, Fig. 1) of the three series of solutions containing (i) known amount of free acid (HNO_3), (ii) known amount of the ligands, HL (NBSS, NBST or NBSM, as the case may be) containing the same amount of free acid (HNO_3) as in (i), and (iv) known amounts of free HNO_3 and the ligand (HL) as in (iii) in presence of a known amount of metal ions ($M^{2+} = Co^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}). For all the three ligands, the maximum value of $\bar{n}$ in the buffer region, pH 5–7.5 was 2, indicating the formation of the complexes $M(H_{-1}L)$ and $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$ (Fig. 2). For the NBSS ligand, further increase of $\bar{n}$ from 2 to 3 in the case of Ni^{2+} -NBSS and 2 to 4 in the cases of Co^{2+} - and Zn^{2+} -NBSS systems were observed at higher pH (9.5–12). These higher pH buffer regions for the NBSS systems could be explained by assuming deprotonation of $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$ complexes according to the equilibria :

The deprotonation constants, $K_{M(H_{-1}L)_2}^H$ ($=c$) and $K_{M(H_{-2}L)_3}^{2H}$ ($=d$), where, $K_{M(H_{-2}L)_3}^{2H} = K_{M(H_{-1}L)_2}^H \cdot K_{M(H_{-2}L)_3}^H$, were evaluated by solving the

formulation function,

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(2+3cx^2/[H]+4dx^3/[H]^2)}{(1+cx^2/[H]+dx^3/[H]^2)} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. $\bar{n}$, pH curves at 35°: (1) NBSS, (2) NBSS-Co^{II}, (3) NBSS-Ni^{II}, (4) NBSS-Zn^{II}, (5) NBST, (6) NBST-Co^{II}, (7) NBST-Ni^{II}, (8) NBST-Zn^{II}, (9) NBSM, (10) NBSM-Co^{II}, (11) NBSM-Ni^{II} and (12) NBSM-Zn^{II}.

which is the extended form of the function (3) applicable in the higher pH buffer region, where the formation of $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$ is complete and the concentrations of the free M^{2+} (aq) ions and those of the complexes $M(H_{-1}L)$, were negligible. The constants a , b , c and d were obtained by graphical solution of different forms of the function (6) using the experimental values of pH, $\bar{n}$ and $\log x$. Preliminary values of the formation constants^{15,16} and the refined values of the constants together with the associated thermodynamic parameters are stated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

With regard to acidity of the carboxylic acid group the ligands were found to be in the order: NBSS > NBST > NBSM. Oxygen atom of the R groups of NBSS and NBST could exert electron withdrawing inductive effect on the deprotonation of COOH group. Lower acidity of NBST as compared to NBSS was probably due to the electron releasing methyl substituent in the R group. For longer carbon chain and lower electronegativity of S atom, the R group of NBSM was not electron withdrawing, in fact, to some extent it was electron releasing. Moreover, there was greater possibility of stabilisation of the carboxylate anions derived from NBSS and NBST as compared

to that from NBSM through intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the sulphonamido and/or the R group involving the formation of chelate rings. Two such chelate rings were possible with the carboxylate anions derived from NBSS and NBST while only one was possible with the carboxylate anion derived from NBSM.

Positive entropy change (ΔS) associated with deprotonation of the ligands (HL) are in good agreement with this proposition.

The predominant form of the ligands in the pH range of complex formation (eqm. 1, 2) with M^{2+} (Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) ions were the carboxylate anions (L^-). As the buffer region corresponding to deprotonation eqm. of the carboxylic acid group of the ligands was not lowered in the presence of these metal ions, it was concluded that carboxylate group was not bonded to metal ions in the complexes $M(H_{-1}L)$ and $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$. Large positive entropy change accompanying the formation of these complexes indicated the formation of chelate structures. Small positive enthalpy changes were in conformity with the deprotonation of the ligand L^- ions during complex formation. The ligands (L^- ions) derived from NBSS and NBST could offer bidentate (N, O) chelation to M^{2+} ions using the sulphonamido nitrogen and hydroxylic oxygen atoms of the R groups, while the L^- ion derived from NBSM could offer bidentate (N, S) chelation using the sulphonamido nitrogen atom and the sulphur atom of the mercaptomethyl residue. Overall stability of Zn^{II} complexes were found to be in the order: NBSS > NBST > NBSM. Stability of $Zn^{II}(d^{10})$ -complexes are due mainly to the electrostatic factors as there could be no ligand field contribution. Lower stability of Zn^{II} -NBSM complex was probably due to smaller electrostatic contribution of the (N, S) donor sites. Lower stability of NBSM complexes as compared to those derived from NBSS were probably due to unfavourable steric effect caused by the methyl substituent in the R group of NBST. Stability orders for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were: NBSM > NBSS > NBST. This was because the stability of $Co^{II}(d^7)$ - and $Ni^{II}(d^8)$ -complexes are sensitive to ligand field stabilisation, and NBSM with its (N, S) donor sites could produce a stronger ligand field than those provided by (N, O) donor sites of NBSS and NBST. Release of protons from the $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$ complexes

derived from NBSS probably involved deprotonation of the coordinated hydroxyl group promoted by oxygen to metal σ -bonding. Such deprotonation of the complexes derived from NBST probably occurred at much higher pH values due to electron releasing effect of the methyl substituent adjacent to the OH group and could not, therefore, be followed pH-metrically. Absence of any deprotonation equilibria for the $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$ complexes derived from NBSM in spite of the π -acidic nature of the sulphur donor atom, ruled out the possibility of deprotonation of coordinated water in the $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{2-}$ complexes derived from NBSS.

All the three ligands formed their most stable complexes with Zn^{2+} . Such an observation is of tremendous biological significance, as out of these three metal ions Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , nature preferentially selects Zn^{2+} ion as the co-factor in certain enzymic processes.

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